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Rethinking India's Approach to Tackle Impact of Climate Change on Agriculture: A Post-Pandemic Scenario

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Abstract

Crop Failures due to unfortunate weather conditions have become prevalent, resulting in a heavy loss for Indian farmers. The concern stems from the flawed logic of the Green Revolution, which relied excessively on science and technology to reduce the food deficit in the country, while largely negating their socio-cultural implications. This is reflected heavily in the government's Economic Survey in 2017–18 which has an exclusive chapter that covers climate change and its impact on agriculture in India. This paper argues that unprecedented reliance on modern technology should be thoroughly checked. The solution is to efficiently address the impact of climate change on agriculture by routing it through an agro-ecosystem, which would deploy both ecological and methodological designs for long-term management of soil fertility and enhancement of agricultural produce.

Keywords: Climate Change, Agroecosystem, Green Revolution, Soil Fertility

Crop failures due to unfortunate weather occurrences, including long spells of drought and extreme precipitation, have become commonplace for the farming community in India. Climate change not only casts a shadow on the productivity of farming but also severely undermines the farmer's planning for crop production, which is integral for a successful harvest. The gravity of the situation can be gauged from a study by the Centre for Science and Environment, which revealed that various manifestations of climate change damaged at least 18 million hectares of crops in 2015 (Bhushan et al., 2015). Similarly, the Parliamentary Standing Committee on Agriculture has pegged the loss due to climate change in the ranges of 4.5–9 per cent of the agricultural economy annually, making for an overall GDP loss of 1.5 per cent (Lok Sabha Secretariat, 2017).

Systematic changes in climate patterns due to anthropogenic activities have a compounding impact on agriculture in terms of an increase in the vulnerability to pest infestation, reduction in the absorption rate of the

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fertilisers and lowering of the nutritional quality of the food grains. The problem is accentuated in the country not only because farming is based on climate variables like monsoon showers but also because of higher initial temperatures, degradable land and the absence of adequate adaptation technologies.

The country is unarguably going through one of the worst phases of agricultural distress in recent years, visible in the form of unabated farmer suicides and mounting farm loans, and the breakout of the novel coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) has just worsened the situation. Though the government claims to have taken measures to improve the general plight of farmers, the issue of climate change and agriculture seems to be conspicuously absent from the discourse. This inaction comes at a time when the Economic Survey of 2018 using district-level data on temperature, rainfall and crop production documented a long-term trend of rising temperatures, a decline in average precipitation and an increase in extreme weather events. Applying these estimates to long-term weather patterns, the survey predicted that climate change could reduce agricultural incomes by as much as 25 per cent for Indian farmers (Lok Sabha Secretariat, 2017).

The present incumbent's distaste for farmers and farming is evident from the Economic Survey itself, which makes a strong assertion to shift people out of agriculture, citing economic and social critiques. While on the economic front, government invokes the Lewisian model of development, which argues that development is always and everywhere about getting people out of agriculture; on the social front, it (mis)quotes Dr Ambedkar to make a critic of villages where he famously derided the village as "a sink of localism, a den of ignorance, narrow mindedness and communalism." Not only does it quote Ambedkar out of context, it also conflates "rural" with agriculture. More importantly, this is a classic manifestation of the identity crisis that is now gripping Indian agriculture. The 'Smart-City' model of development is taking India towards a future that is unsustainable: where rural 'Bharat' does not have any real identity leading to a sense of marginalisation, negligence and inferiority vis-à-vis urban India. India imposed the strictest and longest lockdown in the world during the pandemic, restricting the movement of people and goods that affected the harvesting of rabi crops due to the unavailability of labourers. Farmers already in debt could not find labourers to work in their fields, resulting in them losing a good amount of fortune. The pandemic along with posing physical health risk added to the psychological challenges faced by the poor farmers. Many farmers could not even send their produce to the mandis due to restrictions on movement, and even the mandis remained closed during the initial period of the lockdown (Francisco Ceballos et al., 2020). Therefore, providing institutional help and reducing interest rates will go a long way in helping distressed farmers amid the pandemic.

Cash crops were most affected due to the lockdown as their production depended on the availability of the migrant labourers and the realisation price of the previous season (Ananth, 2020). This resulted in a sharp increase in vegetable and cash crop prices due to the unprecedented changes in the cropping patterns (Ananth, 2020). Thus, the pandemic has added to the plight of farmers of India (Binita Timilsina et al., 2020).

In reality, the fate of India's farmers was sealed when Pandit Nehru had decided to aggressively industrialise India, much against the will of Mahatma Gandhi who believed in empowering villages by making them self-sufficient. It must also be mentioned that Gandhi was not against modernisation or technological advancement. That vision of India is long gone and cannot be re-imagined in an aggressively neo-liberal economy. Nevertheless, if peasants in India are to endure, they need to be safeguarded from multinational companies controlling seed, machinery and fertilisers, the life-lines of a modern Indian farmer. This dependency of farmers on external factors may be squarely blamed on the predicament created by the Green Revolution, often hailed as the saviour in times of dire need. The logic of Green Revolution, which relied excessively on science and technology to solve the puzzle of food security without worrying about its socio-cultural cost, is now reflected in the government's climate change action plan for the agriculture sector.

Predicament of Green Revolution and Technology

The Economic Survey has identified the aggressive expansion of irrigation as the primary adaptation measure to address climate change's perils on agriculture. This is largely based on the premise that the impact of climate change on agriculture is relatively less in irrigated areas as compared to the un-irrigated areas. However, it is pertinent to note that mindless expansion of irrigation can exacerbate conditions of climate change and play havoc with the environment. For instance, the unregulated spread of irrigation in Punjab which now has 98 per cent of its farms under assured irrigation has compounded the imminent danger of desertification in the state (Garg, 2017).

Instead of mindless expansion, the focus should be on water usage patterns that would significantly mitigate the risk of climate change on agriculture. It must be noted that the prevailing irrigation systems in India are highly inefficient and energy-intensive, consuming a staggering 83 per cent of the country's water resources (Suhag, 2016). Not only this, there is a 60 per cent vulnerability in groundwater reserves but also the water footprint of the country stands at twice the global average (Suhag, 2016).

Further, the Economic Survey correctly suggests a shift to modern technologies like drip irrigation for efficient water utilisation. However, the

high transaction cost in even accessing subsidies (wherever provided) and steeping operational cost to maintain these systems have largely dissuaded farmers, especially with small holdings to adopt such techniques. In fact, recent studies have revealed that the existing drip irrigation technologies have failed to adequately penetrate the dry patches of the country where most of the underprivileged and marginalised sections of the society live (Harsha, 2017).

The National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC) was released by the government in 2008, and it issued eight missions. These missions are extremely ambitious and most of them lack funding and implementation. The data provided under the National Water Mission to map all water bodies is unreliable as it uses outdated techniques and methods, thus making the implementation of the programme difficult. The plan to promote sustainable habitats to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions is largely restricted to urban habitats (Estimates Committee Report, 2018). Therefore, all attempts at addressing climate change need strict implementation and adequate funding.

Another narrowly tailored technology-centric approach is the Agricultural Demand-Side Management programme that seeks to replace the current irrigation pumps with energy-efficient models capable of drawing more water with limited electricity. Again, while the scheme has a noble intent of achieving irrigation efficiency, the reality of high water demand and subsidised electricity in most parts of the country results in the pumps running for long periods, in effect, accelerating further depletion of the groundwater level.

The government should learn from its past failures. A recent investigation by CSE also revealed that National Innovation in Climate Resilient Agriculture (NICRA), the central government's pilot programme to address the risk of climate change, has largely been a failure (Venkatesh et al., 2018). The report further revealed that the government's programme, which was launched in 2010 and covers 151 villages most vulnerable to extreme weather, failed to adequately interact with other rural development programmes and reduce its successive budgetary outlays and over-reliance on technological fixes that are neither scalable nor sustainable. These factors have left the farming communities unconvinced and vulnerable. The government recently also commissioned the Ramthal Marola Project—the largest drip irrigation project in Asia—to a private company Megha Engineering and Infrastructures Ltd in Bhagalkot district of Karnataka. Reports show that irrigation is very sensitive in the country, and this may be the reason for the late introduction of privatisation. In the past, India had seen massive protests against the privatisation of the power sector, and there was global unrest against water privatisation in the late 1990s (Diwedi et al., 2007). There was also fierce resistance to early private projects like Sheonath. Scholars have written

against privatisation of water (or water-related projects) in the past, highlighting its failure.

Agroecosystem: The Way Ahead

It is time we realise that resilience to climate change cannot be developed on this flawed model of development that focuses solely on modern technology. While technological interventions can play a functional role, such as dissemination of information through Internet and Communication Technologies (ICTs), they are ultimately stop-gap measures that cannot work without an overhaul of the system within which the Indian agriculture operates. Agro-ecological practices that invoke sustainable productivity increase through climate-adaptation measures could instead play an instrumental role in this direction.

Agro-ecosystem is the application of ecological concepts and methodological designs for the long-term enhancement of soil fertility and management of agricultural productivity. As a strategy, it incentivises diversification of agro-ecosystems and promotes the incorporation of plant and animal biodiversity, nutrient recycling, biomass creation and growth through the use of natural resource systems based on legumes, trees and incorporation of livestock. Further, as a social movement, it pursues multifunctional roles for agriculture, promotes social justice, nurtures identity and culture, and strengthens the economic viability of rural areas.

An important aspect of the agro-ecosystem is to integrate traditional knowledge structures with existing scientific knowledge. Farmers' knowledge and experience of adaptation and innovation have enabled them to cope with extreme weather and environmental change over the years. Identifying, harvesting and scaling up the existing body of knowledge and grass-root innovations along with simple farming techniques like the use of organic fertilisers can play a big role in building resilience to climate change.

For instance, nearly 150,000 farmers in Andhra Pradesh cultivating about 60,000 hectares have shifted to Zero Budget Natural Farming, a natural farming practice that does not use any artificial chemicals but only microbes and nutrients available in the soil. The farmers additionally make use of natural fertilisers like cow dung and jaggery to enrich the soil quality. Similarly, farmers in Nagaland have been encouraged to adopt climate-resilient, traditional food crops along with the revival of conventional practices like jhum or shifting cultivation to reinforce crop diversity.

All said and done, while the Economic Survey rightly suggests diversification away from the cereal centricity of Indian agriculture, government policies have largely acted against it. Dominant agricultural policies in India are

geared towards promoting patterns of mono-cropping. However, the absence of MSPs, ready procurement markets and expertise for other crops mean that the farmers have little incentive to diversify their production patterns.

There is a need to improve the efficiency of resource utilisation instead of narrowly concentrating on the expansion of irrigation. For example, faced with severe drought, Tanzania introduced rice-farming techniques that used less water. This technique is now used by nearly one-third of Tanzanian rice producers, and along with the use of climate-tolerant seed varieties, it has resulted in a four-fold increase in production in the country. Another example is of Vietnamese farmers who were faced with a dire situation of food insecurity after 70,000 hectares of rice and other food crops were heavily damaged by climate-induced natural disasters in 2016. They turned to agroforestry systems, which helped them to not only diversify their income but also control soil erosion, and in turn, improve ecosystems and the environment. In addition, they helped reduce GHG emissions and sequester carbon.

An effective crop insurance scheme is also required to compensate for the uncertainty caused by climate change. However, existing insurance policies that only benefit insurance companies are far from the remedy required to deal with climate change. Studies have shown that climate change being a perfect moral storm (with an unprecedented variety of variables) requires a unique genus of crop insurance. For instance, insurance schemes based on weather-based and crop-specific models that compensate farmers within weeks have been helpful in Kenya to address farmers' woes to some extent.

Climate resilience in the agriculture sector needs to be holistically built. It needs the careful attention of a range of specialists and cannot be developed by focusing on isolated aspects of agriculture. Climate change, with its immense complexity and unfathomable variability, stares deep into the tired and moist eyes of our poor Indian peasants. It is high time that the Indian government realigns its worldview of agriculture and comes to the farmers' rescue.

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